

Title: Short-term Scheduling of a Multi-Purpose Batch Plant Considering Degradation Effects

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Abstract

As is typical of degradation in process industries, fouling often results in significant negative effects on the efficiency of plants. In a batch reactor for example, fouling in external heat exchangers leads to an increased pressure drop across the exchangers resulting in a smaller recirculation flow. Once the pressure drop approaches an unacceptable level, the reactor section needs to be shut down and cleaned. Additionally, the fouling can also prolong batch durations by limiting the cooling capacity. The fouling exacerbates the production bottleneck and therefore needs to be actively considered when doing any scheduling for that batch process.

This paper considers a case study, where production tasks with different recipes contribute to the fouling evolution differently from batch to batch depending on their sequence. The scheduling of the production tasks is improved by explicit consideration of the degradation effects, resulting in an optimized production sequence. A systematic approach is proposed for optimal scheduling of multi-purpose batch processes where the degradation is sequence-dependent. The scheduling problem is formulated using a precedence model with a continuous-time representation [1,2,3]. Regarding the degradation effects, a batch-based fouling model [4] is employed to indicate and predict the fouling evolution over the production regimes, and a reaction stage time model is used to model the fouling effects on batch durations. Integrated with the degradation models, the overall scheduling problem is formulated as a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) and solved using a commercial MILP solver.

To the authors' knowledge, integration of batch-based fouling models in short-term scheduling using a precedence model is novel, and this optimal scheduling is simulated for the case study with different short-term scheduling scenarios. These scenarios demonstrate that the production task sequence is optimized such that the overall capacity is higher comparing to the scheduling which does not consider fouling effects.

References

- [1] Méndez, C. A., Cerdá, J., Grossmann, I. E., Harjunkoski, I., & Fahl, M. (2006). State-of-the-art review of optimization methods for short-term scheduling of batch processes. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 30(6-7), 913-946.
- [2] Harjunkoski, I., Maravelias, C. T., Bongers, P., Castro, P. M., Engell, S., Grossmann, I. E., ... & Wassick, J. (2014). Scope for industrial applications of production scheduling models and solution methods. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 62, 161-193.
- [3] Hadera, H., Harjunkoski, I., Sand, G., Grossmann, I. E., & Engell, S. (2015). Optimization of steel production scheduling with complex time-sensitive electricity cost. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 76, 117-136.
- [4] Wu, O., Bouaswaig, A. E., Schneider, S. M., Leira, F. M., Imsland, L., & Roth, M. (2018). Data-driven degradation model for batch processes: a case study on heat exchanger fouling. In *Computer Aided Chemical Engineering* (Vol. 43, pp. 139-144). Elsevier.

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